

THE IMPACT OF CV AND PERSONALITY ANALYSIS ON THE RECRUITMENT PROCESS: THE CASE STUDY OF TURKEY

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Abstract:

In the era of economic globalization and knowledge economy, science and technology are not only the focus of competition among countries but also the focus of competition among enterprises. The most significant competition in the science and technology fields is related to human resources. For this reason, the recruitment and retention of the talent suitable for the development of the organization has become the center and origin of sustainable development and competitiveness. The traditional recruitment emphasizes on matching people to positions. An individual's knowledge, skills, and abilities are important to follow and fulfill the needs of a position in the best way. Therefore, the person-position recruitment model had become important for a certain period. However, this approach ignores the effects of individuals and other organizational factors on organizational development. In this approach, the degree of the match between recruited individuals and individual and organizational culture values cannot be estimated, and this leads to some adjustment problems. Therefore, there was a necessity to make some changes in the traditional recruitment model. If there is a new position, it should not only be called to fill it, candidates should be seen as individual psychological entities. In the new period, the focus was on the attitudes, character traits, and even hobbies of the employees. Before the companies decided on a candidate, they began to compare these features with their current teams' and employees' features. This approach helps a new employee to adjust himself/herself to the organization more easily and help the company save more time and money.

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1. Introduction

In the article entitled "Transitions to personality-oriented interviews rather than resume focus in the recruitment process in Turkey", the concept and importance of the personality-oriented interview which is one of the interview methods is described.

Most of us update our CVs to prepare ourselves for a job application. We write everything, and moreover, we think that every beauty will come with our CVs. In fact, we think that rather than CV, the people in front of us will measure the criteria such as liking us, addressing team spirit, having a successful self-confidence. However, the person sitting in front of us was hired after a CV screening and since the person is also interviewing us during the recruitment process, we expect something close to the impossible which isn't very unreasonable indeed; then, if our CVs are not up-to-date and not as required, our personalities are of no importance to us.

Thanks to a personality-oriented interview, the recruited new staff will be more easily adapted to the work and workplace, and the risk of person-to-organization compliance will be minimized. In this way, it will be ensured that businesses choose the right staff. In other words, they select the right personnel not only on the paper but also in terms of person-organization compliance. Thus, job leaves will be reduced, and the organizational culture will continue to progress healthily.

Employees form the biggest power of a company, for which companies want their employees to be compatible with their work and workplace. In this regard, in addition to conducting a business analysis, personality analysis of candidates holds an important place. For this reason, interviews should no longer be done by looking at the resume. It is important for the companies that the candidates for employment should be able to work in fit with current employees. For this reason, companies want the candidates' personalities to be compatible with current employees. In line with these requests, firms tend to focus on personality in recruitment. In a world where globalizing and quick decisions have become a necessity, the thing that is as important as finding the right employee for companies is to preserve (not to lose) this employee.

This article emphasizes that the candidate's personality analysis, attitudes, and behaviors should be compatible with the organizational culture in the new recruitment process and that the interview should look not only at the resume but also at the personality analysis.

1.1. Goals of the Study

In this study, the fact that organizations cannot accommodate strong and robust employment power, which is a common problem among organizations, has been discussed. The job interviews, of course, start with some classic questions. It seems important for the HR specialist to know about the training, skills, or plans of the

candidate, but this cannot and should not be considered the sole criterion for decision-making. However, unfortunately, in traditional hiring processes, answering these questions seems enough to choose the right candidate. The present study aims to emphasize that during the personnel's personality inventory, a personality-oriented recruitment situation should be established by asking certain questions. These questions consist of where he/she sees himself/herself after years, why he/she is the best candidate for this job; in this way, the candidate becomes aware of him/her strengths and weaknesses and whether this is his/her dream job or not. The main goal of this study is to show a transition from CV-focused recruitment to personality-oriented systematic recruitment.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Characteristics of Person-Organization Fit

2.1.1 Framework for Person-Organization Fit Recruitment Model

The person-organization fit recruitment-based model refers to the cooperation between the person and the organization. However, the structures of the persons and organizations are quite complex and involve many factors. Chatman thinks that this approach should be understood from the interactive perspective. The organizational model shown in Figure 1 considers that organizations will attract employees with similar characteristics and select them within the organization. As time goes by, the person carrying the clashing features of the organization can be separated from the organization. Thus the homogeneity of the organization gradually increases while the heterogeneity gradually decreases. This model shows that person-organization fit can improve organizational behavior, norms, and values and personal values, and attitudes.

Table 1: Chatman Person-Organization Fit Model

Source: Chatman, J. A. (1989), "Improving Interactional Organizational Research: A Model of Person-Organization Fit", *Academy of Management Review*, 14(3): 333-349

Kristof comprehensively analyzed the concept of person-organization fit and formed the model of the integration of individual and organization.

All the relationships in the model are shown in table 2. Kristof believes that matching people and organizations have three consequences mentioned below.

First, some of the individuals or organizations meet the needs of others.

Second, the basic characteristics of the person and organization have the same or similar parts.

Third, this situation is associated with the first two conditions. Alternatively, this situation has the characteristics of the first two.

Table 2: Kristof's Person-Organization Fit Model

Source: Kristof, A. L. (1996), "Person-Organization Fit: An Integrative Review of Its Conceptualizations, Measurement, and Implications", *Personnel Psychology*, 49(1): 1-49

2.1.2 Characteristics of a Person-Organization Fit Based Recruitment Model

By understanding the difference between a person-position recruitment model and a person-organization fit recruitment model, person-organization fit recruitment model features can be easily found.

The traditional person-position recruitment model does not take organizational culture and individual character suitability into account, leading to a series of human resource management questions. The main limitations of this model can be summarized as follows:

First, individual business performance is often evaluated as a result of personal competencies and matching tasks.

Second, this model focuses on recruiting new staff, irrespective of retaining qualified personnel. Moreover, in the recruitment process, managers do not consider whether they agree with staff on organizational culture and values or not. Despite the traditional recruitment models, the person-organization fit recruitment model is based on the interaction of people and organizations. The advantages of this model can be summarized as follows:

First, it increases the work performance of employees.

Second, it improves the business attitude of employees. When employees have the same values and goals as an institution, they will feel a sense of responsibility and belonging to that. Third, it can help companies protect talented staff and reduce rotations.

2.2 Person-Organization-Based Recruitment Process

The process of the traditional recruitment model is divided into three stages:

- 1) Identifying the basic requirements for a particular position through business analysis.
- 2) Determining the knowledge, skills, and abilities that should be in every position.
- 3) Designing a selection process to choose candidates with the skills required for the position.

The main way to implement this process is to interview.

However, in the person-organization fit recruitment model, candidates are no longer required to be selected based on their talents, basic knowledge, and skills. In addition, there are many other criteria in this regard including social skills, personal needs, values, and personal interests. Therefore, the process of this new recruitment model should change in many aspects. The main steps are summarized as follows:

2.3 Business Analysis and Organizational Analysis for Vacant Positions

Business analysis is an important basis for the recruitment process. It not only provides the foundation for recruitment but also reduces the occupational blindness in recruitment processes and increases the rate of compliance.

Table 3: The main content of the business analysis

Title	Content
Nature of Position	Duties and responsibilities required for the position (e.g., technical positions, management positions, etc.).
Business Functions	Specific Tasks and Functions.
Position Time Management	How to set working and overtime hours.
Working Area	Working Environment and Working Conditions.
Cause of Position	The value and role of the position for the organization.
Position Conditions	Abilities and qualification requirements for the position; Culture, occupational level, work experience, professional ethics, etc.
Position Fee	Salary, additional benefits, and promotion opportunities.

However, an organizational analysis is necessary for the new recruitment model. The goal of the organizational analysis is to define working tasks based on position characteristics and organizational characteristics and to clarify the basic characteristics of the organization such as organizational culture, values, and targets. The organizational analysis studies four aspects.

2.3.1. Organizational Strategy Analysis

A strategic analysis consists of two parts; environmental analysis and organizational texture diagnosis. The main content is to analyze the internal and external environment of the organization, industrial structure, competitive advantages, and competitive disadvantage. A strategic analysis mainly focuses on the organization's cost management and differentiation strategies.

2.3.2 Organizational Culture Analysis

Organizational culture analysis is based on an analysis of organizational culture survey. Basic methods of dialectical thinking and modern scientific thinking are used to reveal the advantages and disadvantages of organizational culture. In this regard, corporate norms, environmental and behavioral culture are the main components.

2.3.3. Interpersonal and Position-Related Environmental Analysis

Interpersonal and position-related environmental analysis is divided into two dimensions; one is the analysis of leadership or managerial behavior and leadership style, and the other is the character analysis of team members.

2.3.4. Position Analysis

The goal of position analysis is to identify and determine the information, technology, skills, and characters required for a position. As long as a complete and comprehensive analysis of the responsibilities and qualifications required for the position is made, the recruitment process based on the person-organization fit may proceed to the next step.

2.4 Revealing Qualifications Required for Position in Compliance with Analyses

The assessment of the person-organization fit recruitment model is divided into two sections: on the one hand, according to the position analysis, revealing the competencies and skills which employees must have for a position. On the other hand, according to the organizational analysis, revealing the must have values, interests, and personalities of employees. Therefore, the iceberg quality model shown in Figure 4 emerges:

Figure 1: Iceberg Quality Model
(Source: (Wood D., 2013, s. 7), (Campanella, 1999, s. 7))

In Figure 4, the information required for the position in the upper section can be obtained using individual learning or training. General testing and interviews are often used as an indicator of the assessment of these skills. However, via training, it is difficult to obtain “potential” requirements such as personality, self-esteem, which are shown on the lower part of the iceberg since these features are the result of socialization. Therefore, these factors play an important role in the assessment and estimation of individual business performance.

2.5 The Design of Candidate Selection Technology and Match up Degree with The Organization

In the traditional recruitment model, selection techniques are mainly based on interviews. However, the person-organization fit recruitment model needs to identify not only the technical skills of a candidate but also the interpersonal and social skills.

The main selection techniques are as follows:

- CV Analysis;
- Cognition, Motivation, and Interpersonal Skills Tests;
- Interviews;
- Personality Tests;
- Review of job experience.

Although this method is mainly used to test a candidate's technical and interpersonal skills, it can also provide information about organizations to make it easier for job seekers to choose suitable organizations.

We can compare the processes of person-organization fit recruitment model and traditional recruitment models as in Figure 5.

Table 3: Comparison of Two Different Recruitment Models

1. Process	2. Person-Position Fit	3. Person-Organization Fit
4. Evaluation of the working environment	5. Position analysis	6. Organization analysis
7. Individual inferences	8. Information 10. Skills 12. Talents	9. Social skills 11. Personal interests 13. Personal characteristics
14. Imaging technology 15. Design	16. Interview	17. CV analysis 18. Cognition, motivation, and Interpersonal skills tests 19. Interviews with potential Candidates 20. Personality tests 21. Review of job experience

3. Literature Review

3.1 Personality-Focused Interviews

The importance and processes of person-organization fit recruitment model were explained in the previous section. As mentioned in Figure 5, in recruitments based on person-organization fit, in addition to individual CV analysis and technical competency-based interviews, different tools have been developed to understand the personality structures of the candidates. In this process, first, the organization should make its analysis and conclude its structure and culture. Then, in the recruitment process, the necessary tools should be designed to reveal the personal characteristics of the candidates. To give an example from Turkey, widely used career websites where job advertisements are published in try to provide data to determine whether candidates are suitable for both the position and the organization before the initial election by providing inventory tests. In this way, before the interview, by comparing the candidate's data with their criteria, organizations can have an idea about the compliance of the candidate to the organization and position, and his\her character in addition to his/her technical skills.

In addition to these, after CV analysis, tests such as personality skills and personality inventory tests can be performed as mentioned in figure 5. In this way, the eliminations can be conducted before the interviews with the candidates or the questions asked from candidates in the interview phase can be shaped.

If we attempt to study the interview types separately, we can distinguish six different types of interviews:

- 1) One-to-One Interviews.
- 2) Panel Interviews.
- 3) Group of Colleagues (teamwork).
- 4) Sequential Interviews.

- 5) Evaluation Center.
- 6) Phone Calls.

The one-to-one interviews are the interviews where almost all the interview with the candidate is held by one person. The interview is criticized for being too subjective as one person does it. In the case of the interviewer being prejudiced, the interview will have a biased result.

Secondly, in the panel interviews, the candidate is interviewed by more than one department manager in the same firm. Although this type of interview is challenging for candidates, it can be very useful when it is well managed since the candidates will sometimes need to work in more than one department. In such a case, the authorities from each department may have the opportunity to evaluate the candidate on their part.

The third type of interview, which is the group of colleagues' interview, is usually used for the evaluation of candidates in terms of teamwork capabilities. The members of a team with whom the candidate will work choose the candidate among the others. This type is mostly used in project-based jobs. Because teamwork is significantly important in project-based jobs, and the project manager will prefer to work with someone that the team agreed and adapted. Therefore, the candidate staff is interviewed by their colleagues.

In sequential interviews, the candidate conducts interviews one after the other, and a different feature of the candidate is tested in each interview. The difference between this interview type and panel interviews is that each field or department is tested in order and separately. The main advantage of the sequential interviews is that the candidate will feel comfortable and perform each stage individually.

The fifth interview is called an evaluation center. In this type of interview, at least three candidates are interviewed at the same time. Candidates are given a case study; they are given time to analyze these events, and the answers to the case study are discussed after the time is up. During the discussion sections, the candidates are observed and evaluated. Although it is an advantageous method for the evaluation of more than one candidate at the same time, the candidates can be stressed. Being evaluated by three staff will cause the person to get nervous and make mistakes.

The phone call, which is the last type of interview, is a difficult one. Although not much a preferred type in Turkey, it is used in two ways. In the first one, the candidate conducts job application on the phone, and the interviewer makes a preliminary interview with the applicant. Secondly, after a preliminary selection, the first interview is made on the phone, and elimination is held accordingly. In this way, before coming to face-to-face interviews, more information about the candidates is obtained, and the ones who will be called for face to face interviews are clarified. The most important advantage of this method is that it saves time for companies. By talking to the candidates on the phone, it is possible to obtain information about their diction, pronunciation, and how they express themselves.

3.2. Transitions to Personality-Based Interviews in Turkey

It is useful to study the concept of personality tests before going through the personality-based interviews. Personality tests are generally divided into two groups. The first is projective tests, and the second one is objective tests.

The specificity of projective tests is that they are based on interpretation. These are the tests attempting to identify the fears, the imagination, and the subconsciousness of a person. Generally, a shape or an image is shown to the person, and he/she should answer what the shape evokes in his/her mind. Thematic Perception Test can be given as an example in this regard.

In the second type personality test, which is the objective test, there is a "standard score," and these tests cannot be interpreted. In the test, which is conducted by a paper and a pen, the answer options are found on the same sheet, and the person should choose one of the options provided.

The mostly used objective test is the MMPI (Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory). The personality tests are briefly like the ones that are examined above. In transitions to personality-based interviews in Turkey, the developments both experienced in Turkey and the world.

These developments are as follows.

- 1) First of all, with digitalization and the expansion of internet access, the expansion of the contents on the internet, the expansion of the concept of the e-learning called online learning, the human resources experts and managers performing the recruitment process in the organizations have been able to access various information about more effective interview techniques and process management. Digitalization has also made it possible to conduct personal and other tests during the recruitment processes, or other questions to be addressed before the interview, through the internet, and accelerated and facilitated the processes. In addition, by creating resume pools, career sites providing services to many companies in recruitment processes by presenting standardized and generally accepted personality inventory testing services can provide the necessary data before a personality-oriented interview.
- 2) However, with the gradually increasing influence of globalization and by being integrated into the world economy after the 2000s, Turkey began to receive foreign direct investment, especially from European foreign companies after being a member of the customs union in 1995. Compared to Turkish companies, these large global companies, which generally have a much deeper history and more advanced structures, have organized the management processes of the companies that they set up in Turkey within the framework of the procedures at their headquarters. Every stage of human resources management can be evaluated in this context.
- 3) Human resources consulting corporation have started to operate in Turkey in recent years as a result of the effects of the factors mentioned in the second item. These human resources consulting corporations are just focused on recruitment

processes and carry out all current updated recruitment applications in line with the demands of the companies. These companies, specialized in recruitment processes, provide various kinds of services according to the demands of their customers.

- 4) On the other hand, developments in the field of company management and organization management have been continued. These developments also affect recruitment processes. For example, Martin Seligman, for the first time in 1999, pointed out that the psychology science focuses on the non-normal aspects of Man, and don't try to understand and develop the strengths and positive aspects of psychology. Also, he emphasized that the psychology findings should be used to teach people how to be more normal, happier, more successful, and better. (Linley, et al. 2006). The reflection of positive psychology on the organizational setting is manifested by two sub-currents. One of them is positive organizational thinking that stresses positive features in order to sustain the life of the organization in crisis and adverse conditions. The other current is positive organizational behavior which is defined as *"the study and practice on strong aspects and psychological capacities of human resources that are positive-directed and can be measured, developed, and managed effectively for the development of today's working life"* (Lathan's, 2002, Guler, 2009).

Such developments have affected recruitment processes and can shape the personality tests to be carried out.

4. Findings

4.1. Attitude, Behaviors and Skills Training

"Skills training" was used by B. Thomas Golisano for the first time for selections in the field of human resources. Thomas Golisano, the CEO, and the founder of B. Paychex adopted an idea when he began to work in the company in 1971. *"The right attitude here and then the job"* was the company's motto for a long time. (Kuchta & Berg, 2004).

This motto is used as a new recruiting method for the modern world. It is also used by famous international companies such as Southwest Airlines, Google, Apple, The Four Seasons, and Silicon Graphics (Murphy, 2012). The companies which are strong and sometimes have unusual corporate culture do not want to have employees without skills, who just work from 9 to 5 and are rigid and inflexible. They look for smart, reliable, flexible, and even humorous colleagues who can take the initiative if necessary (Schawbel, 2012).

Attitude refers to personal and professional success. People are the windows seeing the world. Therefore, the attitude of an employee is very important and must be considered during the recruitment process (Bartlein, 2002).

Also, the attitudes of people define their behaviors; the behaviors in their private and professional lives toward their colleagues, managers, and even customers.

Furthermore, it defines the image of an institution in the customer's mind. And that's one of the reasons which can seal the fate of an institution (Meredith, 2005).

Attitude is a relatively complex concept to explain the importance of human behavior via the science of psychology. The meaning and the content of the attitude may vary according to the user's theoretical tendency and philosophy. For example, a behaviorist or cognitive psychologist describes this concept in different ways (Budak, 2005). The attitudes are the results of the evaluation of objects, issues, or individuals. They are directly related to emotional, behavioral, and cognitive knowledge. This is called the attitude of ABC. The effect of a person toward stimulants and emotions forms an effective component. An action of a person which is related to stimulant defines the behavioral component. A person's thoughts about a particular object, including facts, information, and beliefs form a cognitive component (Taylor, Peplau, and Sears, 2006).

In the Blackwell Encyclopedia of Organizational Behavior Dictionary (1998), "the attitude is defined as a relatively persistent tendency to emotions, beliefs, and behaviors for specific individuals, ideas, philosophies, issues, or objects." In addition, Elliot Aronson (2007) describes it as "*a hidden evaluation – a true or an evil object*" in his book called "The Social Animal."

Eagly and Chaiken (1993) described attitude as "*a psychological tendency expressed in favor or indifference to some extent by evaluating a particular entity*" in their book called "Attitude Psychology." Since then, they have exposed a new definition which they found it as comprehensive. An evaluated asset is called an attitude object in social psychology. The thing or things that are kept in mind can be considered unconsciously so they can be called attitude objects. The entity or attitude objects cause evaluative reactions that psychologists call behavioral. (Eagly and Chaiken, 2007).

Eagly and Chaiken (2007), they explained the importance and clarity of trends in attitude definitions, rather than their tendency or position, with all three terms being elaborated. The term tendency does not necessarily mean that the remnants of past experiences are permanent or temporary. The term state has temporary meanings, and the term means more permanence in psychology.

While traditional studies often advocate these attitudes, a contemporary view declaring attitudes should be conscious experiences reveals that the mental remains of the attitude may be in a course that is consciously advancing from the unconscious. (Eagly and Chaiken, 2007).

Attitude is a very important subject in social psychology. There are several theories that explain how attitudes are formed and how they change. These theories can be summed up under these headings; learning approaches, motivational approaches, and expectation-value approaches (Taylor, Peplau and Sears, 2006).

The theory of learning is based on the assumption that attitudes are achieved in the same way as other habits. The information and facts about different attitude objects are learned by people. The feelings and values related to these facts are also learned. Attitudes are created through basic learning processes. Information and feelings are obtained through the association process. Reinforcement and punishment are also

among the ways to make learning happen. Imitation is another way; it can be learned by attitudes. Message learning is seemed to be very important to change attitudes. If a message is learned, the change is mostly expected (Taylor, Peplau and Sears, 2006).

The theory of learning also brought the effects into the light. People can be persuaded to associate their effects from one object to another. It should be noted that these attitudes were found to be permanent (Carver ve Scheier, 2008).

Motivational approaches are based on the principle of seeking consistency between people's attitudes and their behaviors. They try to make a balance by changing their behaviors. Expectation-value theory shows that people adopt attitudes that will maximize their gains. The theory of cognitive response suggests that people respond to different aspects of a convincing message, and then, they determine whether they support or reject the subject (Taylor, Peplau and Sears 2006, ss: 134-145).

In addition, the concept of business attitudes is of the utmost importance for companies. Business attitudes can be explained as job satisfaction, commitment to the organization, and perception of organizational support.

Vroom explained the concept of job satisfaction as an emotional response to the role of employees in their work and defined the positive reactions to the person's job as job satisfaction and negative reactions to that as job dissatisfaction. (Vroom, 1967).

Commitment to the organization is called as the effort of those working to achieve the goals and objectives of the organization in order to adopt and internalize the goals and to make efforts in order to stay within the organization. According to Allen and Meyer, organizational commitment can be divided into three groups: emotional commitment, continuity commitment, and normative commitment. (Allen and Meyer, 1990).

The concept of organizational support refers to the situation in which the values of the organization consider the welfare of the employees and have a quality that increases their happiness (Eisenberger, 1986).

5. Conclusions and Suggestions

The main goal of this study is to show how important are the person-organization fit, attitude as a motivation theory, and skill training in enterprises in Turkey and across the world. In this study, which is also aimed at searching different perspectives on the subject in different sectors, when considering the studies conducted with other institutions, during the recruitment process, employers try to understand the suitability of the candidate to the company culture and this conformity is one of the most important factors for decision-making. To give importance to the corporate culture and to recruit among the candidates who are suitable for the culture are also the important features of international companies (Schawbel, 2012). Assumptions, specified or unchanged values, norms, customs and rituals, stories and myths, metaphors and symbols, organizational members' climate, and material signs (artifacts) and behaviors constitute an organizational (institutional) culture (Gardner et al. 2012 in Schein). The

importance given to the corporate culture coincides with the attitude and skill theory of motivation. Companies prioritize their employees in case of a vacant position. This preference is also common in the United States. The studies conducted by different researchers show that particularly for the management positions, it is an advantage in the recruitment process of their employees or referenced candidates. This election is explained as the familiarity of the candidate's corporate culture.

Institutions are micro-societies. They differ from the larger societies and have different hopes to define the link between the cultures and official institutions. When a company is established, the founder has the power to set the values from the beginning. The identification of this time is easier than to define when and who the values of a large community are. Also, changing the culture in an institution is easier. Recruitments and dismissals can be done by choosing people and avoiding trying to change people's minds. In the literature review, selective coding of data reveals that by maintaining harmony and peace in the workplace, the greatest goal in the recruitment process is to fill the recently unfilled position. And human resources managers believe that this can be done by recruiting people closer to the company culture and closer to their employees.

If employees work well with each other, they believe that things will be done easier, faster, and more accurately. And to understand this, they pay attention to the candidate's attitudes during the recruitment process and try to understand their personality. Because they believe that the personality characteristics of the employee influence peace and harmony in the workplace.

This finding answers the fundamental question that paying attention to the personality characteristics of the candidates may be the motivation behind the recruitment processes in Turkey. The answer is yes. Current study findings have shown that each organization gives some importance to candidates and their behaviors. Like other examples in the world, the responsibility for recruitment in Turkey also pays attention to the attitude and personality of the election process. This research put forth that human resource managers should decide to interview candidates regardless of how well their CVs are. They also use these interviews as a way to get to know the candidate better and to understand their personality. The questions asked in the interviews are mostly to reveal the personality traits of the candidates. And this is used for different methods and different questions. This result answers another research question of this study. Although the CVs of the candidates are important, interviews are more important in the recruitment process in Turkey. This also matches the recruitment processes of famous international companies around the world.

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